

A SUM CONCERNING SEQUENCES

Maohua Le

Abstract . Let $A=\{a(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence of positive integers. In this paper we prove that if the trailing digit of $a(n)$ is not zero for any n , then sum of $a(n)/\text{Rev}(a(n))$ is divergent.

Key words. decimal number, reverse, sequence of positive integers.

Let $\alpha=a_m \dots a_2 a_1$ be a decimal number . Then the decimal number $a_1 a_2 \dots a_m$ is called the reverse of α and denote by $\text{Rev}(\alpha)$. For example , if $\alpha=123$, then $\text{Rev}(\alpha)=321$. Let $S=\{s(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a certain Smarandache sequence such that $s(n)>0$ for any positive integer n . In [1], Russo that proposed to study the limit

$$(1) \quad L(s)=\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N}{\sum_{n=1}^N \text{Rev}(s(n))} .$$

In this paper we prove a general result as follows.

Theorem . Let $A=\{a(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence of positive integers If the trailing digit of $a(n)$ is not zero for any n , then the sum of $a(n)/\text{Rev}(a(n))$ is divergent.

Proof . Let $a(n)=a_m \dots a_2 a_1$, where $a_1 \neq 0$. Then we have

$$(2) \quad \text{Rev}(a(n))=a_1 a_2 \dots a_m .$$

We see from (2) that

$$(3) \quad \frac{a(n)}{\text{Rev}(a(n))} > \frac{1}{10} .$$

Thus, by (3), the sum of $a(n)/\text{Rev}(a(n))$ is divergent . The

theorem is proved.

References

- [1] F. Russo, Some results about four Smarandache U-product sequences, Smarandache Notions J. 11(2000),42-49.

Department of Mathematics
Zhanjiang Normal College
Zhanjiang, Guangdong
P.R. CHINA